

Professional Skills and Instructional Supervisory Capacity Among Faculty of Public Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Sulu

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Abstract

This study assessed the professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity of faculty members in public Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Sulu during the Academic Year 2023–2024. Utilizing statistical tools such as weighted mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples, one-way ANOVA, and Pearson's r correlation, the study analyzed responses from 200 faculty members, of whom 60% were female and 40% were male, indicating a predominance of female educators in public HEIs in Sulu. Findings revealed that faculty members were generally adept at managing the learning environment; developing outcomes, assessments, and curricula; delivering instruction and learner support; fostering a professional environment; adapting to new technologies; and participating in professional growth. They also demonstrated proficiency in instructional supervision,

including identifying teachers' strengths and limitations, designing interventions, providing professional support, collaborating with organizations and communities, and addressing supervisory challenges. Demographic variables such as gender, age, length of service, and educational attainment showed no significant influence on how faculty assessed their professional skills or supervisory capacity. Moreover, those who rated their professional skills as high were likely to rate their instructional supervisory capacity similarly. The findings are consistent with the Professional Skills Model proposed by Asio, Riego, and Lapuz (2019), and Ekyaw's (2014) model on the practices and challenges of instructional supervision, both emphasizing comprehensive skill sets and collaborative strategies essential for effective teaching and supervision in higher education.

Keywords: *Professional skills, Instructional supervision, Higher Education Institutions, Faculty development, Sulu, Teacher effectiveness*

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a pivotal role in socio-economic and political development, serving as a foundation for progress in nearly all nations. Its effectiveness, however, is largely dependent on the competence of educators, as no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers. In light of this, governments

invest significantly in educational systems to develop skilled, knowledgeable, and professional teaching personnel capable of adapting to the evolving needs of society.

In higher education institutions (HEIs), the complexity of instruction continues to grow due to technological advancements and increasingly diverse student needs. This necessitates not only strong professional teaching skills but also robust instructional supervisory practices to ensure the continuous development of faculty and the quality of learning outcomes. Previous research, primarily conducted in Western contexts, has highlighted the crucial role of instructional supervision and professional development in enhancing teacher performance and student achievement. However, there remains a paucity of empirical studies addressing these factors within rural settings in developing countries such as the Philippines.

To address this gap, the present study investigates the level of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity among faculty members of public HEIs in Sulu. Grounded in the frameworks proposed by Asio, Riego, and Lapuz (2019) and Ekyaw (2014), the study examines how these competencies vary according to demographic variables and how they interrelate. The findings aim to provide valuable insights for improving faculty development programs and instructional quality in rural higher education settings.

METHOD

Research Design

A descriptive-correlational research design will be adopted in this study. In 1995, Bless and Higson-Smith introduced the concept of a research design as “a program that guides a researcher in collecting, analyzing and interpreting observed facts.” (p.63). Similarly, Babbie and Mouton (2001:p.75) regard research design as the road map or blueprint by which one intends to conduct a research and achieve his/her research goals and objectives.” Hence, research design method that will be employed in this study, is will describe, quantify, and infer as well as to discover relationships among variables and to allow the prediction of future events from present knowledge or phenomenon of college faculty members, namely: 1) The demographic profile of college faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in terms of Gender, Age, Length of service, and Educational attainment; 2) The level of professional skills; 3) The level of instructional supervisory capacity; 4) The significant difference in the level of professional skills; 5) the significant difference in level of instructional supervisory capacity; and 6) The significant correlation between the levels of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity.

College faculty of public HEIs in Sulu will be the main source of data which will be quantified to answer the research questions in this study. Library and internet researches and publications will be the sources of information that will be used to enrich the theoretical and conceptual frameworks of this research. The data from the respondents will be gathered through the use of survey questionnaires.

Research Locale

This study will be conducted in Sulu among the public HEIs during the Academic Year 2023-2024 with college faculty as respondents. These HEIs are under the direct administration and supervision of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED).

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study will be college faculty of public HEIs in Sulu who are currently employed and teaching at the different colleges regardless of their academic ranks, civil status and status of appointment during the Academic Year 2023-2024.

Table 1. Distribution of the target samples among faculty of public HEIs in Sulu

Public HEIs in Sulu	Faculty
Hadji Butu School of Arts & Trades	20
MSU-Sulu	90
Sulu State College	90
Total	200

Sampling Design

A none-probability sampling design through purposive sampling method will be employed in this study due to resources and time constraints. The use of purposive sampling technique will ensure the representation of gender, age, length of service, and educational attainment variables among college faculty of public HEIs in Sulu.

Data Gathering Procedure

The following steps will be employed in the course of data gathering:

1. A permit to administer the questionnaire will be sought from the Office of the Dean of Graduate Studies, and the Schools Division Superintendent of MBHTE-Sulu; and
2. The launching and administering as well as the retrieval of the questionnaire will be conducted personally by the researcher.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire will be the main instrument to be employed to gather data on the levels of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity of college faculty of public HEIs in Sulu. This instrument will be adapted and patterned, in part from standardized questionnaire used in Ekyaw (2014) and from Asio, Riego and Lapuz (2019).

The research instrument to be used in this study consisted of three parts. Part I of the questionnaire will focus on obtaining the demographic profile of the respondents which include gender, age, length of service, and educational attainment. Part II will be used in obtaining data on the level of professional skills with the following dimensions such as Managing learning environment; Developing Outcomes, Assessment and Curricula; Providing learner instruction; Providing support and guidance to learners; Creating and maintaining a professional environment; Learning and adapting new technologies; and Participating for Professional Growth and Development. Part III of the research instrument will deal with level of instructional supervisory capacity of college faculty with the following dimensions such as Identification of the strengths and limitations of teachers in the classroom, Designing of various interventions so as to assist teachers, Provision of professional support to teachers, Collaborate schools with various organizations and community groups, and Challenges of secondary schools instructional supervision. A 5-

point Likert-Scale will be used to measure the variables subsumed under the levels of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity.

Validity and Reliability

The research instrument to be used in this research will be patterned and adapted from standardized questionnaires which have been used in previous studies. However, to suit its applicability to the local settings, these questionnaires will be subjected for perusal of at least two experts from among the faculty members of the Graduate Studies of Sulu State College.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive and inferential statistical tools will be appropriately employed in the treatment of data to be gathered for this study, namely:

1. For research question number 1, frequency counts and percentages will be employed to determine the demographic profile of respondents;
2. For research question number 2, mean and standard deviation will be employed to determine the level of professional skills;
3. For research question number 3, mean and standard deviation will be employed to determine the level of instructional supervisory capacity;
4. For research question number 4, t-test for independent samples will be employed to determine the significant differences in the level of professional skills when data are grouped according to gender; and One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) when data are grouped according to age, length of service, and educational attainment.
5. For research question number 5, t-test for independent samples will be employed to determine the significant differences in the level of instructional supervisory capacity when data are grouped according to gender; and One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) when data are grouped according to age, length of service, and educational attainment.
6. For research question number 6, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson's r) will be employed to determine the significant correlation between professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity.

The following rating scales intervals will be adopted in the analyses of the results of the computations to be yielded by both descriptive and inferential statistical tools:

- A. Rating Scales Interval on respondents' levels of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity based on 5-point Likert's Scale:

Point	Scale Value	Descriptors
5	4.50-5.00	Very High Level
4	3.50-4.49	High Level
3	2.50- 3.49	Moderate Level

2	1.50- 2.49	Low Level
1	1.00- 1.49	Very Low Level

B. Rating Scales Interval on respondents' levels of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity based on 5-point Likert's Scale:

Point	Scale Value	Descriptors
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree /Very High Level
4	3.50-4.49	Agree /High Level
3	2.50- 3.49	Undecided /Model Level
2	1.50- 2.49	Disagree /Low Level
1	1.00- 1.49	Strongly Disagree /Very Low Level

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter deals with the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the data gathered for this study. Specifically, it presents the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of: Managing learning environment; Developing Outcomes, Assessment and Curricula; Providing learner instruction; Providing support and guidance to learners; Creating and maintaining a professional environment; Learning and adapting new technologies; and Participating for Professional Growth and Development; The level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of: Identification of the strengths and limitations of teachers in the classroom; Designing of various interventions so as to assist teachers; Provision of professional support to teachers; Collaborate schools with various organizations and community groups; and Challenges of instructional supervision; Difference in the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped in terms of: Gender; Age; Length of service; and Educational attainment; Difference in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped in terms of: Gender; Age; Length of service; and Educational attainment; and correlation between the levels of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu.

The following are the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the proper scoring and statistical treatments of data gathered for this study that which correspond to each of the research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of faculty of HEIs in Sulu in terms of: 1.1 Gender; 1.2 Age; 1.3 Length of service; and 1.4 Educational attainment?

1.1 In terms of Gender

Table 1.1 reflects the demographic profile of faculty of HEIs in Sulu in terms of gender. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 200 faculty-respondents, 80 (40.0%) are male, and 120 (60.0%) are female. This result reveals that more three-fourth or great majority of the total faculty-

respondents involved in this study are female teachers. This result implies that majority of the faculty of HEIs in Sulu are predominantly female college teachers.

Table 1.1 Demographic profile of faculty of HEIs in Sulu in terms of gender

Gender	Number of Teachers	Percent
Male	80	40.0%
Female	120	60.0%
Total	200	100%

1.2 In terms of Age

Table 1.2 shows the demographic profile of faculty of HEIs in Sulu in terms of age. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 200 faculty-respondents, 26 (13.0%) are 30 years old & above, 152 (76.0%) are 31-40 years old, 13 (6.5%) are 41-50 years old, and 9 (4.5%) are 51 years old & above. This study reveals that more than three-fourth or great majority of the total faculty of HEIs in Sulu involved in this study is within 31-40 years old of age bracket. This result implies that majority of the faculty of HEIs in Sulu are belonged to the middle age group as classified in this study.

Table 1.2 Demographic profile of faculty of HEIs in Sulu in terms of age

Age	Number of Teachers	Percent
30 years old & below	26	13.0%
31-40 years old	152	76.0%
41-50 years old	13	6.5%
51 years old & above	9	4.5%
Total	200	100%

1.3 In terms of Length of service

Table 1.3 shows the demographic profile of faculty of HEIs in Sulu in terms of length of service. This table reveals that out of 200 faculty-respondents, 57 (28.5%) have 5 years & below, 130 (65.0%) have 6-10 years, 8 (4.0%) have 11-15 years, and 5 (2.5%) have 16 years & above. This result reveals that majority of the faculty-respondents have been in teaching profession for about 6-10 years. This result implies that, there is considerable number of the faculty of public HEIs in Sulu, who have just enough years of teaching experience. Based on their teaching experience, this further indicates that many of the faculty of HEIs in Sulu needs to have just enough ability to discern as to which kind of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity are more adoptable and efficient in dealing with students' learning experiences.

Table 1.3 Demographic profile of faculty of HEIs in Sulu in terms of length of service

Length of Service	Number of Teachers	Percent
5 years & below	57	28.5%
6-10 years	130	65.0%
11-15 years	8	4.0%
16 years & above	5	2.5%
Total	100	100%

1.4 In terms of Educational Attainment

Table 1.4 shows the demographic profile of faculty of HEIs in Sulu in terms of educational attainment. This table reveals that out of 200 faculty-respondents, 42 (21.0%) have bachelor's degree, 24 (12.0%) have bachelor degree with master's units, 127 (63.5%) have master's degree, 5 (2.5%) have master's degree with doctoral units, and 2 (1.0%) have doctorate degree. This result reveals that great majority of the faculty of HEIs in Sulu have master's degree. This result implies that, there is considerable number of the faculty of HEIs in Sulu who have only the entry requirement for joining the teaching profession at public HEIs. This further indicates that many of the faculty of HEIs in Sulu who remained to have master's degree as their highest educational qualification despite of the availability of graduate programs being offered by most public and private colleges and university in the province of Sulu.

Table 1.4 Demographic profile of faculty of HEIs in Sulu in terms of educational attainment

Educational Attainment	Number of Teachers	Percent
Bachelor's degree	42	21.0%
With master's units	24	12.0%
Master's degree	127	63.5%
With doctoral units	5	2.5%
Doctorate degree	2	1.0%
Total	200	100%

2. What is the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of: 2.1 Managing learning environment; 2.2 Developing Outcomes, Assessment and Curricula; 2.3 Providing learner instruction; 2.4 Providing support and guidance to learners; 2.5 Creating and maintaining a professional environment; 2.6 Learning and adapting new technologies; and 2.7 Participating for Professional Growth and Development?

Table 2.1 shows the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Managing Learning Environment. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 3.8050 with standard deviation of .55000 which is rated as "High Level". This result indicates that faculty-respondents of this study expressed strong agreement that they have very good qualification that is paramount for an effective classroom teacher which enhances and improve teachers teaching skills relative to efficient professional skills. Faculty of public HEIs in Sulu obtained the required equipment, systems, tools, supplies

and materials; set-up and maintain instructional systems, equipment and/or tools; supervise learning environment; and evaluate and monitor the safety of the instructional areas and practices.

It is worth to note that respondents rated the following items as “High Level”, namely: “Obtain required equipment, systems, tools, supplies and materials”, “Set up and maintain instructional systems, equipment and/or tools”, “Supervise learning environment”, and “Evaluate and monitor the safety of the instructional areas and practices”.

Table 2.1 Level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Managing Learning Environment

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Obtain required equipment, systems, tools, supplies and materials.	3.790	.6079	High Level
2	Set up and maintain instructional systems, equipment and/or tools.	3.760	.5881	High Level
3	Supervise learning environment.	3.780	.6754	High Level
4	Evaluate and monitor the safety of the instructional areas and practices.	3.890	.7232	High Level
Total Weighted Mean		3.805	.5500	High Level

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Very High Level; (4) 3.50-4.49= High Level; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderate (2) 1.50-2.49= Low Level; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Very Low Level

2.2 In the context of Developing Outcomes, Assessment and Curricula

Table 2.2 shows the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Developing Outcomes, Assessment and Curricula. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 3.797 with standard deviation of .5489 which is rated as “High Level”. This result indicates that teacher-respondents of this study expressed strong agreement that they have high level of qualification that is paramount for an effective classroom teacher which enhances and improve teachers teaching skills and efficient professional skills. Faculty of public HEIs in Sulu are highly skilled in evaluating and modifying current outcomes; create, evaluate and modify curriculum and assessment; implement curriculum, outcomes and assessment; integrate curriculum with other faculty in the department and in other area/institution; and providing learner instruction.

It is notable that respondents rated the following items as “High Level”, namely: “Identify, evaluate and modify current outcomes”, “Create, evaluate and modify curriculum and assessment”, “Implement curriculum, outcomes and assessment”, and “Integrate curriculum with other faculty in the department and in other area/ institution”.

Table 2.2 Level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Developing Outcomes, Assessment and Curricula

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Identify, evaluate and modify current outcomes.	3.860	.6516	High Level
2	Create, evaluate and modify curriculum and assessment.	3.760	.6215	High Level
3	Implement curriculum, outcomes and assessment.	3.800	.7521	High Level
4	Integrate curriculum with other faculty in the department and in other area/ institution.	3.770	.5835	High Level
Total Weighted Mean		3.797	.5489	High Level

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Very High Level; (4) 3.50-4.49= High Level; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderate (2) 1.50-2.49= Low Level; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Very Low Level

2.3 In the context of Providing Learner Instruction

Table 2.3 shows the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Providing Learner Instruction. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 3.920 with standard deviation of .6122 which is rated as “High Level”. This result indicates that teacher-respondents of this study made strong agreement that they are efficient in preparing and/or gathering current instructional materials and equipment; provide individual and group instruction; initiate, develop and implement student assessment; modify instructional material and methods based on student and industry assessment and feedback; and creating and maintaining a professional environment.

It is remarkable that respondents rated the following items as “High Level”, namely: “Prepare and/or gather current instructional materials and equipment”, “Provide individual and group instruction”, “Initiate, develop and implement student assessment”, and “Modify instructional material and methods based on student and industry assessment and feedback”.

Table 2.3 Level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Providing Learner Instruction

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Prepare and/or gather current instructional materials and equipment.	3.990	.7034	High Level
2	Provide individual and group instruction.	3.940	.6639	High Level

3	Initiate, develop and implement student assessment.	3.800	.7106	High Level
4	Modify instructional material and methods based on student and industry assessment and feedback.	3.950	.6871	High Level
Total Weighted Mean		3.920	.6122	High Level

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Very High Level; (4) 3.50-4.49= High Level; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderate (2) 1.50-2.49= Low Level; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Very Low Level

2.4 In the context of Providing Support and Guidance to Learners

Table 2.4 shows the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Providing Support and Guidance to Learners. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 3.867 with standard deviation of .5789 which is rated as “High Level”. This result indicates that faculty-respondents of this study expressed strong agreement that they are efficient in responding to student needs and provide information or referrals; assist students with job placement; provide academic and career advising; and serve as student activity advisors as applicable.

It is notable that respondents rated the following items as “High Level”, namely: “Respond to student needs and provide information or referrals”, “Assist students with job placement”, “Provide academic and career advising”, and “Serve as student activity advisors as applicable”.

Table 2.4 Level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Providing Support and Guidance to Learners

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 Respond to student needs and provide information or referrals.	4.010	.7176	High Level
2 Assist students with job placement.	3.800	.6195	High Level
3 Provide academic and career advising.	3.780	.6754	High Level
4 Serve as student activity advisors as applicable.	3.880	.6709	High Level
Total Weighted Mean	3.867	.5789	High Level

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Very High Level; (4) 3.50-4.49= High Level; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderate (2) 1.50-2.49= Low Level; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Very Low Level

2.5 In the context of Maintaining a Professional Environment

Table 2.5 shows the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Maintaining a Professional Environment. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 3.737 with

standard deviation of .5917 which is rated as “High Level”. This result indicates that teacher-respondents of this study expressed strong agreement that they are efficient in collaborating with teaching staff, teachers and students; serve on district and school committees; maintain current knowledge of the field; and develop a professional development plan.

Interestingly, respondents rated the following items as “High Level”, namely: “Collaborate with college staff, faculty and students”, “Serve on department and college committees”, “Maintain current knowledge of the field”, and “Develop a professional development plan”.

Table 2.5 Level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Maintaining a Professional Environment

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Collaborate with college staff, faculty and students.	3.850	.7436	High Level
2	Serve on department and college committees.	3.650	.6092	High Level
3	Maintain current knowledge of the field.	3.640	.7319	High Level
4	Develop a professional development plan.	3.810	.7063	High Level
Total Weighted Mean		3.737	.5917	High Level

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Very High Level; (4) 3.50-4.49= High Level; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderate (2) 1.50-2.49= Low Level; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Very Low Level

2.6 In the context of Learning and Adapting New Technologies

Table 2.6 shows the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Learning and Adapting New Technologies. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 3.762 with standard deviation of .6320 which is rated as “High Level”. This result indicates that teacher-respondents of this study expressed strong agreement that they are obtaining and maintaining certification on program-specific technology; maintain current knowledge of technology in the field; identify, evaluate and implement emerging technologies according to industry needs; and identify and evaluate and implement new instructional technologies.

Notably, respondents rated the following items as “High Level”, namely: “Obtain and maintain certification on program-specific technology”, “Maintain current knowledge of technology in the field”, “Identify, evaluate and implement emerging technologies according to industry needs”, and “Identify and evaluate and implement new instructional technologies”.

Table 2.6 Level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Learning and Adapting New Technologies

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Obtain and maintain certification on program-specific technology.	3.790	.7005	High Level

2	Maintain current knowledge of technology in the field.	3.770	.7227	High Level
3	Identify, evaluate and implement emerging technologies according to industry needs.	3.640	.7319	High Level
4	Identify and evaluate and implement new instructional technologies.	3.850	.6871	High Level
Total Weighted Mean		3.762	.6320	High Level

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Very High Level; (4) 3.50-4.49= High Level; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderate (2) 1.50-2.49= Low Level; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Very Low Level

2.7 In the context of Participating for Professional Growth and Development

Table 2.7 shows the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Participating for Professional Growth and Development. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 3.737 with standard deviation of .6270 which is rated as “High Level”. This result indicates that teacher-respondents of this study expressed strong agreement that they are very good in joining and participating in professional organizations, groups, or association within or outside the institution; participate to seminars, assemblies, conventions, colloquium, etc.; initiate and publish a research locally, nationally or internationally; and enroll for higher degrees (Master’s/Doctorate), certification programs and the like.

It is noteworthy that respondents rated the following items as “High Level”, namely: “Join professional organizations, groups, or association within or outside the institution”, “Participate to seminars, assemblies, conventions, colloquium, etc.”, “Initiate and publish a research locally, nationally or internationally”, and “Enroll for higher degrees (Master’s/Doctorate), certification programs and the like.

Table 2.7 Level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Participating for Professional Growth and Development

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Join professional organizations, groups, or association within or outside the institution.	3.850	.6723	High Level
2	Participate to seminars, assemblies, conventions, colloquium, etc.	3.990	.7452	High Level
3	Initiate and publish a research locally, nationally or internationally.	3.440	.8326	High Level
4	Enroll for higher degrees (Master’s/Doctorate), certification programs and the like.	3.670	.7920	High Level
Total Weighted Mean		3.737	.6270	High Level

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Very High Level; (4) 3.50-4.49= High Level; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderate (2) 1.50-2.49= Low Level; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Very Low Level

3. What is the level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of: 2.1 Identification of the strengths and limitations of teachers in the classroom; 2.2 Designing of various interventions so as to assist teachers; 2.3 Provision of professional support to teachers; 2.4 Collaborate schools with various organizations and community groups; and 2.5 Challenges of instructional supervision?

3.1 In the Context of Identification of the strengths and limitations of teachers in the classroom

Table 3.1 shows the level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of identification of the strengths and limitations of teachers in the classroom. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.290 with standard deviation of .5734 which is rated as “High Level”. This result indicates that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu affirmed that there is a high level of the instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu through identification of the strengths and limitations of teachers in the classroom.

Table 3.1 Level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Identification of the strengths and limitations of teachers in the classroom

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Instructional Supervisors regularly identify any instructional limitations of teachers in the classroom	4.255	.7765	High Level
2	Instructional Supervisors identify the lack of abilities to manage students in the classroom	4.220	.8215	High Level
3	Instructional supervisors identify the student evaluation skill gaps of teachers	4.200	.8506	High Level
4	Instructional Supervisors encourage and facilitate school self-evaluation on instructional matters	4.280	.7240	High Level
5	Instructional supervisors facilitate the availability of instructional materials and encourage teachers to use it appropriately	4.305	.7581	High Level
6	Instructional supervisors encourage teachers in developing instructional goals and objectives	4.430	.6982	High Level
7	Instructional supervisors“ advice teachers to use active learning in the classroom	4.445	.6395	High Level
8	Instructional supervisors design appropriate intervention to minimize the identified limitations of teachers in the classrooms	4.185	.6805	High Level
Total Weighted Mean		4.290	.5734	High Level

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Very High Level; (4) 3.50-4.49= High Level; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderate (2) 1.50-2.49= Low Level; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Very Low Level

3.2 In the Context of Designing of various interventions so as to assist teachers

Table 3.2 shows the level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of designing of various interventions so as to assist teachers. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.272 with standard deviation of .5797 which is rated as “High Level”. This result indicates that faculty-respondents are in agreement that there is a high level of the instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu through designing of various interventions so as to assist teachers.

Noticeably, faculty of public HEIs in Sulu rated the following items as “High Level”, among others, namely: “Instructional supervisors are arranging induction training for beginner teachers”, “Instructional supervisors in the school assist teachers in lesson planning”, “Instructional supervisors facilitate experience sharing programs”, “Instructional supervisors assist teachers in developing/selecting instructional materials”, and “Instructional supervisors are spread new teaching methodologies among schools and teachers”.

Table 3.2 Level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of designing of various interventions so as to assist teachers

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Instructional supervisors are arranging induction training for beginner teachers	4.310	.6754	High Level
2	Instructional supervisors in the school assist teachers in lesson planning	4.280	.6884	High Level
3	Instructional supervisors facilitate experience sharing programs	4.315	.7058	High Level
4	Instructional supervisors assist teachers in developing/selecting instructional materials	4.275	.6569	High Level
5	Instructional supervisors are spread new teaching methodologies among schools and teachers	4.275	.7761	High Level
6	Instructional supervisors are facilitating professional growth of teachers through short term training, workshops and seminars	4.330	.7025	High Level
7	Instructional supervisors support teachers to do action research	4.120	.8117	High Level
Total Weighted Mean		4.272	.5797	High Level

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Very High Level; (4) 3.50-4.49= High Level; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderate (2) 1.50-2.49= Low Level; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Very Low Level

3.3 In the Context of Provision of professional support to teachers

Table 3.3 shows the level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of provision of professional support to teachers. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.172 with standard deviation of .6415 which is rated as “High Level”. This result indicates that faculty-respondents are in agreement that there is a high level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu through provision of professional support to teachers.

Noticeably, faculty of public HEIs in Sulu rated the following items as “High Level”, among others, namely: “Supervisors support teachers to prepare different instructional materials on teaching-learning process”, “Instructional supervisors advice teachers to conduct action research”, “Instructional supervisors

facilitate short term training to teachers on new teaching methodologies”, “Instructional supervisor advice teachers to use model effective teaching methods and encourage them to motivate students in the classroom”, and “Instructional supervisors create competition among teachers on pedagogical skills”.

Table 3.3 Level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Provision of professional support to teachers

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Supervisors support teachers to prepare different instructional materials on teaching-learning process	4.330	.7096	High Level
2	Instructional supervisors advice teachers to conduct action research	4.005	.8113	High Level
3	Instructional supervisors facilitate short term training to teachers on new teaching methodologies	4.200	.8082	High Level
4	Instructional supervisor advice teachers to use model effective teaching methods and encourage them to motivate students in the classroom.	4.375	.7328	High Level
5	Instructional supervisors create competition among teachers on pedagogical skills	3.950	.9229	High Level
6	Instructional supervisors facilitate experience sharing programs between teachers	4.175	.7728	High Level
Total Weighted Mean		4.172	.6415	High Level

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Very High Level; (4) 3.50-4.49= High Level; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderate (2) 1.50-2.49= Low Level; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Very Low Level

3.4 In the Context of Collaborate schools with various organizations and community groups

Table 3.4 shows the level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Collaborate schools with various organizations and community groups. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.175 with standard deviation of .6741 which is rated as “High Level”. This result indicates that secondary school teacher-respondents are in unison that there is a high level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu through collaborating schools with various organizations and community groups.

Noticeably, faculty of public HEIs in Sulu rated the following items as “High Level”, among others, namely: “Instructional supervisors link the schools/clusters with the community to discuss on the problems that face on teaching-learning process”, “Instructional supervisors link the schools with local NGOs to solve material and financial problems”, “Instructional supervisors regularly report school problems to all stakeholders”, “Instructional supervisors organize different committees from different stakeholders”, and “Instructional supervisors encourage model parents and NGOs for their active participation in the school”.

Table 3.4 Level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Collaborate schools with various organizations and community groups

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Instructional supervisors link the schools/clusters with the community to discuss on the problems that face on teaching-learning process	4.180	.8191	High Level
2	Instructional supervisors link the schools with local NGOs to solve material and financial problems	4.170	.7964	High Level
3	Instructional supervisors regularly report school problems to all stakeholders	4.150	.8491	High Level
4	Instructional supervisors organize different committees from different stakeholders	4.095	.7804	High Level
5	Instructional supervisors encourage model parents and NGOs for their active participation in the school	4.290	.7407	High Level
6	Instructional Supervisors play roles in community mobilization	4.165	.8130	High Level
Total Weighted Mean		4.175	.6741	High Level

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Very High Level; (4) 3.50-4.49= High Level; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderate (2) 1.50-2.49= Low Level; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Very Low Level

3.5 In the Context of Challenges of instructional supervision

Table 3.5 shows the level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Challenges of instructional supervision. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.117 with standard deviation of .6144 which is rated as “High Level”. This result indicates that faculty-respondents are in solid agreement that there is a high level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu through appreciation of challenges of secondary schools instructional supervision.

Noticeably, faculty of public HEIs in Sulu rated the following items as “High Level”, among others, namely: “Instructional supervisors are overburdened with many tasks”, “Instructional Supervisors are responsible to support beginner teachers instructionally”, “Instructional supervisors teaches the same credit like ordinary teachers”, “Teachers have readiness to accept their instructional limitations”, “Instructional supervisors have financial incentives than teachers”, and “Instructional supervisors are authorized to take remedial actions”.

Table 3.5 Level of instructional supervisory capacity of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of Challenges of secondary schools instructional supervision

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Instructional supervisors are overburdened with many tasks	3.995	.9430	High Level

2	Instructional Supervisors are responsible to support beginner teachers instructionally	4.09 0	.790 5	High Level
3	Instructional supervisors teaches the same credit like ordinary teachers	3.95 0	.906 4	High Level
4	Teachers have readiness to accept their instructional limitations	4.17 5	.732 8	High Level
5	Instructional supervisors have financial incentives than teachers	3.92 5	.940 1	High Level
6	Instructional supervisors are authorized to take remedial actions	4.26 0	.710 5	High Level
7	Instructional supervisors are getting support from MBHTE-Sulu Office	4.25 0	.692 7	High Level
8	Instructional supervisors have their own offices, furniture with stationary materials	4.16 0	.732 8	High Level
9	Instructional supervisors have enough time to support all teachers instructionally	4.18 0	.787 8	High Level
10	Instructional supervisors have enough instructional guidelines	4.18 5	.702 3	High Level
Total Weighted Mean		4.11 7	.614 4	High Level 1

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Very High Level; (4) 3.50-4.49= High Level; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderate (2) 1.50-2.49= Low Level; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Very Low Level

4. Is there a significant difference in the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped in terms of: 4.1 Gender; 4.2 Age; 4.3 Length of service; and 4.5 Educational attainment?

4.1 According to Gender

Table 4.1 illustrates the difference in the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped in terms of gender. It is reflected in this table that all the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of professional skills with their corresponding Mean Differences, t-values and probability values are not significant at alpha .05. This means that male and female faculty-respondents in this study do not differ in their assessment of the level of professional skills. This result implies that being a male respondent may not probably make him better perceiver toward the level of professional skills over his female counterpart, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable gender has no significant intervention in the ways how respondents assess the extent of professional skills. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is

no significant difference in the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to gender” is accepted.

Table 4.1 Differences in the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped in terms of gender

VARIABLES	Grouping	Mean	S. D.	Mean Diff.	t	Sig.	Description
Managing learning environment	Male	3.714	.3934	-	-	.653	Not Significant
	Female	3.714	.3934				
Developing Outcomes, Assessment and Curricula	Male	3.642	.3181	-	-	.442	Not Significant
	Female	3.809	.5619				
Providing learner instruction	Male	3.785	.4661	-	-	.550	Not Significant
	Female	3.930	.6226				
Providing support and guidance to learners	Male	3.714	.2672	-	-	.471	Not Significant
	Female	3.879	.5950				
Creating and maintaining a professional environment	Male	3.642	.2439	-	-	.663	Not Significant
	Female	3.744	.6101				
Learning and adapting new technologies	Male	3.714	.2672	-	-	.835	Not Significant
	Female	3.766	.6519				
Participating for Professional Growth and Development	Male	3.607	.2834	-	-	.571	Not Significant
	Female	3.747	.6453				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

4.2 According to Age

Table 4.2 illustrates the difference in the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped in terms of age. It is reflected in this table that all the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of professional skills with their corresponding F-values and probability values are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, although faculty-respondents in this study vary in age range, yet they do not differ in their assessment of the extent of professional skills. This result implies that a respondent within the age range of 51 years old & above may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of professional skills over those respondents within the age range of 30 years old & below, 31-40 years old, and 41-50 years old, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable age has no significant intervention in the ways how respondents assess the level of professional skills. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to age” is accepted.

Table 4.2 Differences in the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped in terms of age

SOURCES OF VARIATION	Grouping	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square.	F	Sig.	Description
Managing learning environment	Between	.717	3	.239	.785	.505	Not Significant
	Within Groups	29.230	96	.304			
Total		29.948	99				
Developing Outcomes, Assessment and Curricula	Between	1.734	3	.578	1.975	.123	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.103	96	.293			
Total		29.837	99				
Providing learner instruction	Between	1.487	3	.496	1.335	.267	Not Significant
		35.623	96	.371			

	Within Groups						
Total		37.110	99				
Providing support and guidance to learners	Between	.638	3	.213	.628	.599	Not Significant
	Within Groups	32.544	96	.339			
Total		33.182	99				
Creating and maintaining a professional environment	Between	1.232	3	.411	1.179	.322	Not Significant
	Within Groups	33.440	96	.348			
Total		34.672	99				
Learning and adapting new technologies	Between	.423	3	.141	.346	.792	Not Significant
	Within Groups	39.124	96	.408			
Total		39.547	99				
Participating for Professional Growth and Development	Between	2.580	3	.860	-.568	.571	Not Significant
	Within Groups	36.342	96	.379			
Total		38.922	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

4.3 According to Length of Service

Table 4.3 illustrates the difference in the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped in terms of when data are grouped according to length of service. It is reflected in this table that, except for “Developing Outcomes, Assessment and Curricula” all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of professional skills with their corresponding F-values and probability values

are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, although faculty-respondents in this study vary in number of years of teaching experience, yet they do not differ in their assessment of the extent of professional skills. This result implies that a respondent who has been in service for 16 years & above may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of professional skills over those respondents who have been serving for 5 years& below, 6-10 years, and 11-15 years, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable length of service has no significant intervention in the ways how respondents assess the level of professional skills. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service” is accepted.

Table 4.3 Differences in the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service

SOURCES OF VARIATION	Grouping	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Managing learning environment	Between	1.288	3	.429	1.439	.236	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.659	96	.299			
Total		29.837	99				
Developing Outcomes, Assessment and Curriculum	Between	2.997	3	.999	3.574*	.017	Significant
	Within Groups	26.840	96	.280			
Total		29.837	99				
Providing learner instruction	Between	1.613	3	.538	1.454	.232	Not Significant
	Within Groups	35.497	96	.370			
Total			99				

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Creating and maintaining a professional environment	Betw een	.948	3	.31 6	1.1 79	.3 22	Not Significant
	With in Grou ps	32.2 34	96	.33 6			
Total		34.6 72	99				
Learning and adapting new technologies	Betw een	.423	3	.14 1	.34 6	.7 92	Not Significant
	With in Grou ps	39.1 24	96	.40 8			
Total		39.5 47	99				
Participating for Professional Growth and Development	Betw een	2.58 0	3	.86 0	.34 6	.7 92	Not Significant
	With in Grou ps	36.3 42	96	.37 9			
Total		38.9 22	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

4.4 According to Educational Attainment

Table 4.4 illustrates the difference in the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment. It is reflected in this table that all of the

sub-categories subsumed under the extent of professional skills with their corresponding F-values and probability values are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, although faculty-respondents in this study vary in educational qualification, yet they do not differ in their assessment of the extent of professional skills. This result implies that a respondent who has doctorate degree may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of professional skills over those respondents who have bachelor's degree, bachelor's degree with master's units, master's degree, and master's degree with doctoral units, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable educational attainment has no significant intervention in the ways how respondents assess the level of professional skills. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the level of professional skills of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment" is accepted.

Table 4.4 Differences in the extent of professional skills of elementary school teachers at District IV, MBHTE-Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment

SOURCES OF VARIATION	Grouping	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square.	F	Sig.	Description
Managing learning environment	Between	1.042	4	.261	.856	.493	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.905	95	.304			
Total		29.947	99				
Developing Outcomes, Assessment and Curricula	Between	.065	4	.016	.052*	.995	Significant
	Within Groups	29.772	95	.313			
Total		29.837	99				
Providing learner instruction	Between	1.327	4	.332	.881	.479	Not Significant
	Within Groups	35.783	95	.377			
Total		37.110	99				
Providing support and guidance to learners	Between	1.394	4	.349	1.042	.390	Not Significant
	Within Groups	31.788	95	.335			
Total		33.182	99				
Creating and maintaining a professional environment	Between	1.804	4	.451	1.304	.274	Not Significant
	Within Groups	32.868	95	.346			

Total		34.672	99				
Learning and adapting new technologies	Between	1.453	4	.363	.906	.464	Not Significant
	Within Groups	38.094	95	.401			
Total		39.547	99				
Participating for Professional Growth and Development	Between	1.754	4	.438	1.121	.351	Not Significant
	Within Groups	37.168	95	.391			
Total		38.922	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

5. Is there a significant difference in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped in terms of: 5.1 Gender; 5.2 Age; 5.3 Length of service; and 5.4 Educational attainment?

5.1 – According to Gender

Table 5.1 presents the difference in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped in terms of gender. It can be gleaned from this table that, except for “Collaborate schools with various organizations and community” and “Challenges of secondary schools instructional supervision” the Mean Differences, t-values and probability values of other sub-categories subsumed under the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu are generally not significant at alpha .05. This means that, though faculty-respondents in this study vary in their age ranges, generally they do not differ in their perceptions toward the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu. This result implies that being a male college faculty may not probably make him better perceiver toward the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu than his female counterpart, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable gender has no significant influence in the ways how faculty-respondents perceive toward the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to gender” is accepted.

Table 5.1 Differences in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to gender

VARIABLES	Grouping	Mean	SD	Mean Diff.	T	Sig.	Description
Identification of the strengths and limitations of teachers in the classroom	Male	4.396	.5386	.1500	1.687	.093	Not Significant

	Female	4.246	.5832				
Designing of various interventions so as to assist teachers	Male	4.339	.5781	.0954	1.057	.292	Not Significant
	Female	4.244	.5801				
Provision of professional support to teachers	Male	4.284	.6329	.1577	1.584	.115	Not Significant
	Female	4.126	.6416				
Collaborate schools with various organizations and community	Male	4.330	.6871	.2189*	2.102	.037	Significant
	Female	4.111	.6606				
Challenges of secondary schools instructional supervision	Male	4.282	.5831	.2334*	2.469	.014	Significant
	Female	4.049	.6160				

VARIA BLES	Grou ping	Su m of Squ ares	df	Me an Sq uar e.	F	Si g.	Descr iption
Identifi cation of the strength s and limitati ons of teacher s in the classro om	Betw een Grou ps	.711	3	.237	.718	.542	Not Signif icant
	With in Grou ps	64.719	196	.330			
Total		65.430	199				
Designi ng of	Betw een	.795	3	.265	.786	.503	

various interventions so as to assist teachers	Groups						Not Significant
	With in Groups	66.087	196	.337			
Total		66.882	199				
Provision of professional support to teachers	Between Groups	2.683	3	.894	2.212	.088	Not Significant
	With in Groups	79.227	196	.404			
Total		81.910	199				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

5.2 According to Age

Table 5.2 presents the difference in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to age. It can be gleaned from this table that all of the F-values and probability values of all the sub-categories subsumed under the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, though faculty-respondents in this study vary in their age ranges, generally they do not differ in their perceptions toward the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu. This result implies that a college faculty within the age range of 51 years old & above may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu than those within 30 years old & below, 31-40 years old, and 41-50 years old, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable age has no significant influence in the ways how faculty-respondents perceive toward the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to age" is accepted.

Table 5.2 Differences in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to age

Collaborate schools with various organizations	Between Groups	3.010	3	1.003	2.250	.084	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87.420	196	.446			
Total		90.431	199				
Challenges of secondary schools instructional supervision	Between Groups	2.198	3	.733	1.969	.120	Not Significant
	Within Groups	72.944	196	.372			
Total		75.142	199				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

5.3 – According to Length of Service

Table 5.3 presents the differences in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service. It can be gleaned from this table that the F-values and probability values of all the sub-categories subsumed under the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, though faculty-respondents in this study vary in the number of years they have been teaching at public HEIs in Sulu, generally they do not differ in their ways of perceiving the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu. This result implies that a college faculty who has been in teaching profession for 16 years & above may not be a guaranty for him/her to be a better perceiver toward the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu than those teachers who have been rendering teaching services for 5 years & below, and 6-10 years, 11-15 years, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable length of service generally has no significant influence in the ways how faculty-respondents perceive toward the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service” is accepted.

Table 5.3 Differences in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service

VARIABLES	Grouping	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Si g.	Description
Identification of the strengths and limitations of teachers in the classroom	Between Groups	.772	3	.257	.780	.506	Not Significant
	Within Groups	64.658	196	.330			
Total		65.430	199				
Designing of various interventions so as to assist teachers	Between Groups	.326	3	.109	.320	.811	Not Significant
	Within Groups	66.555	196	.340			
Total		66.882	199				
Provision of professional support to teachers	Between Groups	1.065	3	.355	.861	.463	Not Significant
	Within Groups	80.845	196	.412			
Total		81.910	199				
Collaborate schools with various organizations	Between Groups	2.131	3	.710	1.577	.196	Not Significant
	Within Groups	88.299	196	.451			

Total		90.4 31	19 9				
Challenges of secondary schools instructional supervision	Between Groups	.682	3	.227	.598	.617	Not Significant
	Within Groups	74.4 60	19 6	.380			
Total		75.1 42	19 9				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

5.4 According to Educational Attainment

Table 5.4 presents the difference in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment. It can be gleaned from this table that except for sub-category “Identification of the strengths and limitations of teachers in the classroom”, all of the F-values and probability values of all other sub-categories subsumed under the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, though faculty-respondents in this study vary in the level of their educational attainment, generally they do not differ in their ways of perceiving the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu. This result implies that a college faculty who has a doctorate degree may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu than those teachers having bachelor’ degree, bachelor’s degree with master’s units, master’s degree, and master’s degree with doctoral units, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable educational attainment has no significant mediation in the ways how faculty-respondents assess the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment” is accepted.

Table 5.4 Differences in the level of instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment

VARIABLES	Grouping	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Si g.	Description
Identification of the strength	Between Groups	3.118	4	.780	2.439*	.048	Significant

s and limitations of teachers in the classroom	With in Groups	62.312	195	.320			
Total		65.430	199				
Designing of various interventions so as to assist teachers	Between Groups	1.709	4	.427	1.278	.280	Not Significant
	With in Groups	65.173	195	.334			
Total		66.882	199				
Provision of professional support to teachers	Between Groups	2.683	3	.894	2.230	.067	Not Significant
	With in Groups	79.227	196	.404			
Total		81.910	199				
Collaborate schools with various organizations	Between Groups	3.774	4	.943	2.123	.079	Not Significant
	With in Groups	86.657	195	.444			
Total		90.431	199				
Challenges of secondary schools	Between Groups	2.801	4	.700	1.887	.114	Not Significant
	With in	72.341	195	.371			

instru ctiona l superv ision	Group s						
Total		75.1 42	19 9				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

6. Is there a significant correlation between the levels of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu?

Table 6 illustrates the correlation between the levels of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu. It can be gleaned from this table that the computed Pearson Correlation Coefficients (Pearson's r) between these variables are significant at alpha .05.

Specifically, the degree of correlations between the levels of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu is as follows:

Generally, there is a high positive correlation between the levels of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu.

This result indicates that the college faculty of public HEIs in Sulu who generally assessed the level of professional skills as "High Level" is most probably the same group of college faculty of public HEIs in Sulu who assessed instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu as "High Level" respectively.

Meanwhile, it is safe to say that, generally the levels of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu are highly correlated.

Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant correlation between the levels of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu" is rejected.

Table 6. Correlation between the levels of professional skills and instructional supervisory capacity of faculty of public HEIs in Sulu

Variables		Pearson r	Sig	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Professional Skills	Instructional Supervisory Capacity	.544**	.000	200	High

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):

0.0-0.1=Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.30=Low; .3-0.5 0=Moderate; .5-0.7-0=High; .7-0.9= Very High; 0.9-1=Nearly Perfect

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